

A Study of Pre-Operative Predictors of Difficult Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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Abstract:

Background: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is the preferred surgical treatment for gallbladder diseases due to its minimally invasive nature and reduced recovery time. However, some cases present significant challenges, leading to increased operative time, higher conversion rates to open surgery, and elevated risks of complications. The study aims to investigate the preoperative predictors in difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Methods: A total of 100 patients undergoing LC were included based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Pre-operative factors such as age, gender, BMI, previous hospitalization, palpable gallbladder, biochemical markers, and ultrasonographic findings were analyzed. The difficulty of each surgery was recorded, and a scoring system was developed to predict the operative difficulty.

Results: Out of 100 patients, 64% had easy surgeries, 33% had difficult surgeries, and 3% had very difficult surgeries. Significant predictors of difficult LC included male gender ($p=0.0001$), previous hospitalization ($p=0.001$), palpable gallbladder ($p=0.0001$), elevated biochemical markers ($p=0.0001$), thickened gallbladder wall ($p=0.005$), and pericholecystic collection ($p=0.0001$). The developed scoring system demonstrated high predictive values, with an AUC of 0.86, sensitivity of 89.9%, and specificity of 81.8%.

Conclusion: The study successfully identified several pre-operative predictors of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The scoring system developed provides a reliable method for pre-operative assessment, allowing better surgical planning and improved patient counseling.

Recommendations: Future studies should focus on further validating the scoring system in larger and more diverse populations. Incorporating additional predictors such as advanced imaging techniques may enhance the accuracy of the scoring system. Surgeons should consider these predictors when planning for LC to minimize complications and improve outcomes.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, Pre-Operative Predictors, Surgical Difficulty, Scoring System, Gallbladder Surgery.

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Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is the gold standard treatment for gallbladder diseases, particularly cholelithiasis and cholecystitis, due to its minimally invasive nature, shorter recovery times, and reduced postoperative pain compared to open cholecystectomy. Despite its advantages, a significant proportion of LC procedures can be technically challenging, leading to increased operative time, higher conversion rates to open surgery, and elevated risks of complications. Consequently, identifying pre-operative predictors of difficult LC is crucial for surgical planning and patient counseling.

Recent studies have focused on developing and validating pre-operative scoring systems to predict the difficulty of LC. These scoring systems

incorporate various clinical, biochemical, and radiological factors that have been shown to correlate with increased operative difficulty. For instance, a study developed a risk score based on an objective grading system, demonstrating that factors such as male gender, high body mass index (BMI), and previous episodes of acute cholecystitis significantly predict difficult cholecystectomies [1].

Gender has been a consistent predictor, with multiple studies indicating that males are more likely to experience difficult LC. This could be attributed to the higher incidence of acute cholecystitis and a generally more robust inflammatory response observed in males. Additionally, obesity, indicated by a BMI greater than 30, poses technical challenges during LC due

to limited visualization and increased difficulty in maneuvering instruments [2].

Previous hospitalizations for acute cholecystitis also serve as a significant predictor. Patients with a history of severe gallbladder inflammation often present with dense adhesions and distorted anatomy, complicating the surgical procedure. Ultrasonographic findings, such as a thickened gallbladder wall and the presence of pericholecystic fluid, have been validated as reliable predictors of difficult LC. These findings are indicative of chronic inflammation and fibrosis, which can obscure anatomical landmarks and hinder dissection [3].

The integration of biochemical markers, such as elevated liver enzymes and bilirubin levels, into predictive models has further enhanced their accuracy. These markers reflect underlying hepatobiliary pathology, which often correlates with more challenging surgical scenarios. The use of comprehensive scoring systems that combine these parameters has proven effective in stratifying patients according to their risk of encountering difficult LCs. For example, a study confirmed the utility of such a scoring system in predicting both the difficulty of LC and the likelihood of conversion to open surgery [4].

The study aims to investigate the preoperative predictors in difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Methodology

Study Design: The study was a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: This study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery at Deen Dayal Upadhyay Hospital and Hedgewar Arogyasri sansthan New Delhi, a 300-bedded tertiary health care centre. The study was conducted over a period from 2022 to 2024.

Study Population: A total of 100 patients were included in the study after obtaining written informed consent.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients aged between 20 and 80 years presenting with symptoms and signs of cholecystitis/post-ERCP status and diagnosed by ultrasound examination in the Surgery department.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients below 20 years of age and above 80 years of age.

- Patients with common bile duct calculus or dilated common bile duct where common bile duct exploration is needed.
- Asymptomatic patients of cholelithiasis.
- Pregnant females.
- Patients with refractory coagulopathy.
- Patients unfit for anesthesia.
- Patients with gallbladder malignancy.
- Patients refusing surgery.

Sample Size: This study was conducted on 100 patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The sample size was calculated based on the prevalence of gallbladder wall thickness in easy and difficult patients from a previous study. Using a formula for sample size calculation [5], a sample size of 79 was deemed necessary for the study to achieve 80% power and a 5% significance level with 0.09 precision.

Method of Collection

The method for the study included patients presenting with symptoms or signs of cholecystitis. Detailed clinical examinations were performed, and all routine preoperative investigations were conducted, including:

- Complete blood count
- Liver function test
- Kidney function test
- Random blood sugar
- Electrocardiogram
- Chest X-ray
- PT/INR (Prothrombin/International normalized ratio)
- Viral markers
- Blood group
- Ultrasound of the whole abdomen

Patients confirmed by ultrasound examination were evaluated for factors including age, sex, history of hospitalization for acute cholecystitis/jaundice/pancreatitis, body mass index, palpable gallbladder, abdominal scar supra-umbilical or infra-umbilical, sonographic findings (wall thickness, pericholecystic collection, impacted stone). All patients were operated on by one surgical unit.

Data Collection during Surgery

Following evaluation, the patients underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy, and data were collected on operative time, biliary/stone spillage, injury to duct/artery, or conversion to open surgery. All cases were followed for any early postoperative complications.

Figure 1: Creation of pneumoperitoneum by Veress needle insertion in supraumbilical position

Figure 2: Port placement in supra-umbilical position

Figure 3: Further port placement in sub-xiphoid region, right subcostal region in mid-clavicular line, right lumbar region in anterior axillary line

Figure 4: two and only 2 structures entering into the gall bladder- cystic duct and cystic artery

Figure 5: dense adhesions of duodenum with gall bladder in difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Figure 6: Dense adhesions of omentum and duodenum with gall bladder in difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Statistical Analysis: Results were presented in frequencies, percentages, and mean \pm SD. The Chi-square test was used to compare categorical/dichotomous variables, and the unpaired t-test was used to compare continuous variables. The receiving operating curve (ROC) analysis was performed, and the area under the curve (AUC) with its 95% confidence interval (CI) was calculated. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) with their 95% CIs were calculated. A

p-value of <0.05 was considered significant. All analyses were performed using SPSS version 16.0.

Result

The study aimed to identify clinical, biochemical, and radiological predictors of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy. A total of 100 patients were included in the study. The study found no significant association between age and intra-operative difficulty. Patients aged <50 years were more common (74%).

Table 1a: Association of Pre-operative Predictors with Intra-operative Difficulty

Factor	Category	No. (n=100)	Easy	Difficult	Very difficult	p-value
Age (years)	<50	74	47	24	3	0.57
	≥ 50	26	17	9	0	
Gender	Male	24	8	16	0	0.0001*
	Female	76	56	17	3	
Previous Hospitalization	Present	32	14	18	0	0.001*
	Absent	68	50	15	3	
BMI (kg/m ²)	<30	81	54	24	3	0.10
	≥ 30	19	10	9	0	

Table 1b: Association of Pre-operative Predictors with Intra-operative Difficulty

Factor	Category	No. (n=100)	Easy	Difficult	Very difficult	p-value
Upper Abdominal Scar	Present	29	12	15	2	0.05
	Absent	71	52	18	1	
Palpable Gall Bladder	Present	7	1	4	2	0.0001*
	Absent	93	63	29	1	
Biochemical Parameters	Total Bilirubin	29	7	21	1	0.0001*
	SGOT/SGPT	32	10	20	2	
	Alkaline Phosphatase	33	9	23	1	
Wall Thickness	Thick	24	9	13	2	0.005*
	Thin	76	55	20	1	
Pericholecystic Collection	Present	23	8	12	3	0.0001*
	Absent	77	56	21	0	
Impacted Stone	Present	15	3	12	0	0.0001*
	Absent	85	61	21	3	

A significant association was found between gender and intra-operative difficulty. Difficulty was higher among male patients. A significant association was found between previous history of hospitalization and intra-operative difficulty. No significant association was found between BMI and intra-operative difficulty. There was a nearly significant association between upper abdominal scar and intra-operative difficulty. A significant association was found between palpable gall bladder and intra-operative difficulty.

A significant association was found between raised biochemical parameters (total bilirubin, SGOT/SGPT, and alkaline phosphatase) and intra-operative difficulty. A significant association was found between gallbladder wall thickness and intra-operative difficulty. A significant association was found between pericholecystic collection and intra-operative difficulty. A significant association was found between impacted stone and intra-operative difficulty. The scoring system used in this study had high predictive values for difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Table 2: Predictive Value of Scoring System for Prediction of Difficult Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

Scoring System Cut Off	Pre-op Prediction		Total
	Difficult	Easy	
>3	80	2	82
≤3	9	9	18
Total	89	11	100
Predictive Values			
AUC	0.86 (0.76-0.97), p=0.0001		
Sensitivity	89.9 (83.6-96.2)		
Specificity	81.8 (59.0-104.6)		
PPV	97.6 (94.2-100.9)		
NPV	50.0 (26.9-73.1)		

The preoperative prediction score was significantly higher among patients with difficult (6.07 ± 2.15) than easy (2.27 ± 2.01) laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Figure 7: ROC curve showing sensitivity and specificity scoring system for prediction of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Discussion

The study examined 100 patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy to identify pre-operative predictors of surgical difficulty. Among the patients, 64% experienced easy surgeries, 33% faced difficult surgeries, and 3% encountered very difficult surgeries. This distribution highlights that while the majority of laparoscopic cholecystectomies are straightforward, a significant portion presents challenges that require additional attention and expertise.

Several pre-operative factors were found to be significantly associated with intra-operative difficulty. Male patients had a notably higher likelihood of encountering difficult surgeries compared to female patients, with a significant p-value of 0.0001. This suggests that gender may be an important factor to consider when assessing the risk of surgical complications.

Patients with a history of hospitalization for acute cholecystitis, jaundice, or pancreatitis were significantly more likely to have difficult surgeries ($p=0.001$). This indicates that a patient's medical history plays a crucial role in predicting surgical outcomes.

The presence of a palpable gall bladder was strongly associated with increased surgical difficulty ($p=0.0001$). This physical finding should alert surgeons to potential challenges during the procedure.

Elevated levels of total bilirubin, SGOT/SGPT, and alkaline phosphatase were significantly linked to difficult surgeries ($p=0.0001$ for each parameter). These biochemical markers can be used as indicators of potential complications during laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Patients with thickened gall bladder walls and pericholecystic collections were more likely to experience difficult surgeries ($p=0.005$ and

$p=0.0001$, respectively). These ultrasonographic findings are valuable in pre-operative evaluations to predict surgical difficulty.

The presence of impacted stones was also significantly associated with increased surgical difficulty ($p=0.0001$). This suggests that detailed imaging and assessment of stone position are essential in pre-operative planning.

The scoring system used in this study demonstrated high predictive values for identifying difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy cases. A pre-operative score greater than 3 was highly indicative of a difficult surgery, with a sensitivity of 89.9% and a specificity of 81.8%. The scoring system's area under the curve (AUC) was 0.86, indicating excellent predictive accuracy.

The mean pre-operative prediction score was significantly higher among patients with difficult surgeries (6.07 ± 2.15) compared to those with easy surgeries (2.27 ± 2.01), with a p -value of 0.001. This finding underscores the effectiveness of the scoring system in differentiating between easy and difficult cases.

The results of this study highlight several key pre-operative predictors that can help in anticipating the difficulty of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Factors such as gender, previous hospitalization, palpable gall bladder, elevated biochemical parameters, wall thickness, pericholecystic collection, and impacted stones are significant indicators of potential challenges during surgery. The scoring system used in the study provides a reliable method for pre-operative assessment, enabling surgeons to better prepare for and manage difficult cases, ultimately improving patient outcomes and reducing the risk of complications.

A prospective study assessed a scoring system for predicting difficult cholecystectomies in 208 patients with symptomatic gallstones. The study found that 75.5% of the patients were predicted to have an easy cholecystectomy, while 24.5% were expected to face difficulties. The scoring system demonstrated high sensitivity (96.5%) and moderate specificity (68.5%), with positive predictive values of 89.1% for easy cases and 72.5% for difficult ones [6].

Research investigated predictors of difficulty in LC, identifying significant factors such as palpable gallbladder, history of cholecystitis, gallbladder wall thickness, pericholecystic fluid, and impacted stones. The modified Randhawa scoring system used in this study showed a sensitivity of 90.9% and a specificity of 73.1%, indicating its effectiveness in preoperative prediction [7].

An observational study was conducted to identify risk factors for difficult LC. Their findings highlighted the significance of previous

hospitalizations, obesity, palpable gallbladder, and gallbladder wall thickness. The preoperative scoring system used in this study showed an accuracy of 85.6%, making it a reliable tool for predicting surgical difficulty [8].

A study evaluated clinical and radiological factors in predicting difficult LC. The study found significant predictors, including age over 50, male sex, BMI greater than 27.5, and palpable gallbladder. The scoring system demonstrated good sensitivity (74.3%) and high specificity (96.9%), indicating its utility in preoperative assessments [9].

A study identified factors such as a history of hospitalization, palpable gallbladder, impacted stones, and gallbladder wall thickness as significant predictors of difficult LC. Their study showed that the preoperative scoring system had a sensitivity of 95.74% and a specificity of 73.68%, supporting its effectiveness in predicting surgical outcomes [10].

Furthermore, a study focused on the reliability of preoperative scoring systems in predicting LC difficulty. Factors like male sex, obesity, and gallbladder wall thickness were identified as significant predictors. The scoring system's sensitivity was found to be 82.3%, with a specificity of 72.7%, demonstrating its predictive value [11].

Conclusion

This study successfully identified several pre-operative predictors of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy, including male gender, previous hospitalization for acute cholecystitis, palpable gallbladder, elevated biochemical markers, thickened gallbladder wall, and pericholecystic collection. The developed scoring system provides a reliable method for pre-operative assessment, allowing for better surgical planning and improved patient counseling. Implementing such predictive tools can help surgeons anticipate potential complications, optimize surgical outcomes, and ensure informed decision-making for patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Future research should focus on validating this scoring system in larger and more diverse populations to enhance its predictive accuracy.

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